

Large-scale individual tree species mapping using AVIRIS-NG and LiDAR data fusion

Audrey Lambiel^{*1}, Loïc Gerber², Anna K. Schweiger³, Mathias Kneubühler⁵, Grégoire Mariéthoz², Anthony Lehmann^{1,4}, Nathan Külling¹

¹ EnviroSPACE Laboratory, Institute for Environmental Sciences, University of Geneva, Bd. Carl-Vogt 66, 1205 Geneva, Switzerland

² GAIA Lab, Institute of Earth Surface Dynamics, University of Lausanne, Géopolis, 1015 Lausanne, Switzerland

³ Department of Land Resources and Environmental Sciences, Montana State University, 325 Leon Johnson Hall, Bozeman, MT 59717, USA

⁴ Department. F.-A. Forel of Aquatic and Environmental Sciences, University of Geneva, Bd. Carl-Vogt 66, 1205 Geneva, Switzerland

⁵ University of Zurich, Department of Geography, Remote Sensing Laboratories, Winterthurerstrasse 190, 8057 Zürich, Switzerland

* Corresponding author: Audrey Lambiel. EnviroSPACE Laboratory, Institute for Environmental Sciences, University of Geneva, Bd. Carl-Vogt 66, 1205 Geneva, Switzerland.

E-mail: audrey.lambiel@unige.ch

0. Abstract

Accurate tree species mapping is critical for effective forest management and ecosystem monitoring, especially under climate change. Mapping species composition is essential for understanding ecological dynamics, which supports conservation and sustainable resource management. However, traditional field-based monitoring is time-consuming and resource-intensive, particularly in mountainous regions. This study explores the use of remote sensing and machine learning techniques to improve the efficiency and accuracy of individual tree crown (ITC)-level species mapping. We utilize imaging spectroscopy data from NASA's AVIRIS-NG sensor covering the 400 to 2400 nm spectral range with 425 bands and 2-meter spatial resolution, offering a great opportunity for high-resolution vegetation analysis. Our study area covers 630 km² within the Swiss Pre-Alps. A Random Forest classifier was trained to identify five dominant tree species. Model performance was evaluated using ground reference points and compared with classifications derived from Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery and structural features extracted from airborne LiDAR. The spectral model achieved strong predictive performance (Overall accuracy = 0.74). LiDAR-derived structural features provided marginal improvements when incorporated into the spectral model but performed poorly when used independently. Multispectral data produced limited classification accuracy. To address spatial gaps from incomplete flight coverage, we applied the tile-based gap-filling algorithm *chessQS* to generate a continuous, high-resolution species map. This study presents the first application of AVIRIS-NG data for tree species mapping in the Swiss Pre-Alps and demonstrates its potential for large-scale, high-precision forest monitoring in complex mountainous environments.

Keywords: imaging spectroscopy, hyperspectral, vegetation classification, Swiss Pre-Alps

1. Introduction

In times of climate change and biodiversity loss, advanced methods for ecosystem monitoring are needed to guide effective conservation strategies and management plans (Cavender-Bares et al., 2022; Lahoz-Monfort & Magrath, 2021). Forests provide a series of Nature's Contributions to People (NCP - Díaz et al., 2018), such as timber, food production, carbon sequestration, erosion control, and recreation, supporting environment stability and human well-being (Mori et al., 2017; Olschewski et al., 2018). In Switzerland, forests cover about 30% of the national territory, providing critical protection against natural hazards, sustaining rural economies, and hosting nearly 35% of the country's species (OFEV, 2022). However, forests in Switzerland and beyond are increasingly threatened by effects of climate change, including rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns and increasing frequency and severity of extreme weather events (CH2018, 2018). These threats make forests more vulnerable to pests, diseases and fires, all of which can alter forests composition (OFEV/WSL, 2025). Preserving forest integrity under these conditions requires adaptive management strategies supported by accurate monitoring of forest dynamics and species composition (Mori et al., 2017; Strassburg et al., 2020), as emphasized by international and national policies including the United Nations Strategic Plan for Forests (UN, 2017) and the revised Swiss Forest Policy (OFEV, 2021).

Accurate vegetation mapping is essential for effective forest conservation and management (Mori et al., 2017; Walpole et al., 2017). Until recently this task relied on labor-intensive field

surveys, limiting spatial coverage and assessment frequency (Xie et al., 2008; Zhong et al., 2024). Since the 1970s, and particularly following the launch of the first Landsat satellites, remote sensing technologies have significantly advanced vegetation monitoring, enabling broader and more frequent assessments (Matyukira & Mhangara, 2024; Xie et al., 2008). Recent decades have seen an increased use of remote sensing for species-level forest mapping (Fassnacht et al., 2016), a pre-requisite for analyzing complex ecological dynamics at large scales (Ghiyammat & Shafri, 2010). Such maps support a wide range of applications, including biodiversity monitoring, species distribution modeling, or NCP assessments (Gholizadeh et al., 2019; Jha et al., 2019) enabling targeted conservation measures and sustainable forest management plans (Guisan et al., 2013; Walpole et al., 2017).

Imaging spectroscopy is an advanced optical remote sensing technique that captures continuous reflectance spectra for every pixel, providing substantially richer spectral information than traditional multispectral sensors. When acquired with hundreds of contiguous bands, these measurements constitute imaging spectroscopy data, which capture subtle biochemical and biophysical differences among plant species (Fassnacht et al., 2016; Yel & Tunc Gormus, 2023). We use airborne AVIRIS-NG data as our imaging spectroscopy dataset. By leveraging the full spectral signature, reflecting plant form and function, imaging spectroscopy enables detailed characterization of vegetation optical properties and improves species discrimination, even when structural traits overlap (Kothari & Schweiger, 2022). These spectral signatures can thus be used for tree species classification (Ahmad et al., 2021; Yel & Tunc Gormus, 2023; Zhong et al., 2024).

Light detection and ranging (LiDAR) complements imaging spectroscopy by capturing the three-dimensional structure of forest canopies, providing geometric information that enhances species classification (Balestra et al., 2024; Michałowska & Rapiński, 2021). Integrating spectral and structural data has been shown to improve classification accuracy by 5–20%, especially in multi-layered forests (Jiang et al., 2025; Quan et al., 2023; Shi et al., 2018; B. Wang et al., 2023). While airborne imaging spectroscopy offers significant advantages for species classification, their use is often challenged by data gaps due to cloud cover of acquisition inconsistencies. These gaps can compromise spatial continuity and statistical consistency of classification outputs, that is the preservation of both spatial patterns and class distributions across the landscape, essential for continuous and accurate species maps (Gerber et al., 2025; Q. Wang et al., 2023). Various gap-filling techniques have been developed (Q. Wang et al., 2023), among which Multiple-Point Statistics (MPS) have gained recent attention for their ability to preserve high-order spatial patterns (Gerber et al., 2025).

This study advances species-levels forest mapping in complex mountainous environments through the integration of cutting-edge remote sensing technologies. Specifically, we present the first application of imaging spectroscopy data from NASA's Airborne Visible-Infrared Imaging Spectrometer (AVIRIS-NG), combined with airborne LiDAR to classify tree species at the individual crown level in the Swiss Pre-Alps. Our objectives are threefold: (1) to leverage imaging spectroscopy techniques for tree species classification, demonstrating its potential for high-resolution vegetation mapping; (2) to evaluate the added value of imaging spectroscopy data by comparing its classification performance with that of commonly used datasets, Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery and LiDAR-derived structural features; and (3) to produce a comprehensive and accurate tree species map while exploring the use of multi-point statistics to fill image gaps. By integrating AVIRIS-NG and LiDAR data, this work enables accurate,

large-scale mapping of tree species in terrain traditionally difficult to monitor, providing valuable insights for adaptive forest management.

2. Material and methods

This section outlines the study workflow (Figure 1). The process involved five main steps: (1) acquisition of remote sensing and ground reference data; (2) data preprocessing, including extraction of spectral information and LiDAR metrics for each ground reference point; (3) training of four Random Forest models using data combinations; (4) post processing and evaluation of model performance; and (5) generation of a high-resolution tree species map for the study area.

Figure 1 – Workflow for tree species classification using remote sensing data and Random Forest models. The approach integrates LiDAR point clouds, AVIRIS-NG imaging spectroscopy data, Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery, and combines them with ground reference points. The process involves data preparation, features extraction and selection, model training, prediction, evaluation, and post-processing to produce a high-resolution tree species map. Analysis was performed in R (R Core Team, 2022), with imaging spectroscopy data pre-processing conducted in ENVI (Exelis Visual Information, 2023).

2.1. Study area

Our study was conducted in the Gruyère Pays d’Enhaut (GPH) Regional Nature park, located in the Swiss Pre-Alps (Figure 2) (Pays-d’Enhaut, 2025). Covering an area of 632 km², the park spans an elevation range from 374 to 2,548 meters (Swisstopo, 2022a) and is characterized by a diverse mosaic of vegetation types (Pays-d’Enhaut, 2025). Forests occupy about 38% of the park’s area and are dominated by common spruce (*Picea abies*; Pa), silver fir (*Abies alba*; Aa), common beech (*Fagus sylvatica*; Fs), sycamore maple (*Acer pseudoplatanus*; Ap) and common ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*; Fe) (Brändli et al., 2020). This heterogeneous landscape, combined with steep topography, presents a great challenge for large-scale species mapping and makes the region an ideal test site for evaluating the added value of imaging spectroscopy data.

Figure 2 – Study area and data coverage. Map of the Gruyère Pays-d'Enhaut regional nature park (red line), showing AVIRIS-NG flightlines (green stripes) and ground reference points (yellow dots). Insets indicate the park's location within Switzerland and Europe. Elevation data are shown for Switzerland at the national scale.

2.2. Data acquisition

2.2.1. Imaging spectroscopy data

AVIRIS-NG is a state-of-the-art imaging spectroscopy sensor developed by NASA operated by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (<https://aviris.jpl.nasa.gov/>). This high-resolution data sensor is widely used for detailed vegetation mapping and species classification (Ahmad et al., 2021; Fassnacht et al., 2016; Jha et al., 2019; Yel & Tunc Gormus, 2023).

Imaging spectroscopy data was acquired during flights over the park on July 10th, 2021, under clear weather conditions (Schweiger, 2021), resulting in 18 images (425 spectral bands), hereafter called flightlines, with spatial resolution ranging from 1.70 m to 2.40 m (Figure 2), and covering 490 km² of the study area. Each pixel contains ground reflectance values across wavelengths from 377 nm to 2,501 nm with 5 nm interval.

Images were first reprojected to the Swiss coordinate system (EPSG: 2056) using the ‘terra’ package (Hijmans, 2023) and geometrically corrected using ENVI 5.6 registration workflow (Jin, 2018) with SwissIMAGE Level 3 color orthophotos (Swisstopo, 2022b) as reference. Corresponding points were identified, including automatically generated and manually added features such as road intersections, to ensure precise alignment. This process was applied to all 18 flightlines, with reference points uniformly distributed. The Root Mean Square Error

(RMSE) was maintained within 1 m, which is considered acceptable (Xie et al., 2008). Spectral bands known to be uninformative for vegetation classification (e.g. water absorption bands) were excluded, retaining 319 bands covering of 412-1,304 nm, 1,464-1,774 nm and 2,030-2,411 nm (Jha et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019). Specifically, bands 1 - 7, 187 - 217, 281 - 330 and 408 - 425 were removed.

To reduce redundancy and processing time, dimensionality reduction was performed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Badola et al., 2021; Jha et al., 2019).

2.2.2. Sentinel-2

Multispectral data was retrieved from the Copernicus database (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/browser/>). Sentinel-2B Level-2A (atmospherically corrected) imagery were acquired on July 23, 2021, selected to closely match the imaging spectroscopy data acquisition date and ensure minimal cloud cover over the study area.

Sentinel-2 provides 13 spectral bands covering visible, red edge, and shortwave infrared regions, spanning wavelengths from 443 nm to 2,190 nm. These bands enable detailed analysis of vegetation, water, soil and atmospheric conditions. Bands with 20 meters resolution were reprojected to the Swiss coordinate system (EPSG: 2056) and resampled to 2 m resolution using the ‘terra’ package (Hijmans, 2023).

2.2.3. LiDAR

Airborne LiDAR data were used both to delineate individual tree crowns (ITC) and as structural metrics in tree classification models. Data were obtained from the swissSURFACE3D product, acquired between 2018 and 2019 (Swisstopo, 2021). The dataset provides a point density of 15-20 pts/m² (minimum 5 pts/m²) with horizontal and vertical accuracy of ± 20 cm and ± 10 cm, respectively. Each point is classified into one of the following categories: ground, vegetation, buildings, water, bridges, or unclassified.

LiDAR data processing was performed using the ‘lidR’ package (Roussel et al., 2020). Tiles covering the study area were normalized using a digital terrain model (DTM) (Plakman et al., 2020). Then, the z-coordinates of points classified as “built”, “bridge” or “non-classified” were set to 0 to exclude non-vegetation elements from further analysis.

2.2.4. Field survey

Ground reference points were collected between May 31st and June 13th, 2022 (Figure 2) to train and test the model. A regular 2-km grid was applied across the study area, and 30 accessible units, defined as locations within 500 m of a road and on moderate slopes, were randomly selected. Each unit aimed to include approximately 25 trees, corresponding to an overall density of about 3 trees per km² across the 240 km² of forested area, similar to comparable remote sensing studies (Dalponte et al., 2014).

Within each unit, we recorded the precise location of five target tree species, *Abies alba* (Aa), *Acer pseudoplatanus* (Ap), *Fraxinus excelsior* (Fe), *Fagus sylvatica* (Fs) and *Picea abies* (Pa), using a Trimble R2 GPS/GNSS system (Trimble, Westminster USA) with an RTK service (swipos-GIS/GEO). The GPS device was positioned as close as possible to the crown center, and only canopy-top trees were sampled. To minimize mixed spectral signatures, trees were required to (1) either have a crown diameter ≥ 3 m or be located within a same-species patch, and (2) be at least 3 m away from features such as roads or buildings.

In total, 747 trees were sampled (Figure 2), with balanced representation across species: *Abies alba* (110), *Acer pseudoplatanus* (141), *Fagus excelsior* (150), *Fagus sylvatica* (151), and *Picea abies* (195).

2.3. Comparative analysis of multispectral, imaging spectroscopy and LiDAR-based models

To evaluate the contribution of different remote sensing datasets to tree species classification, we trained four Random Forest (RF) models using distinct input combinations: (1) Imaging spectroscopy-based model, using reflectance values extracted from AVIRIS-NG imaging spectroscopy data; (2) Multispectral-based model, which uses reflectance values extracted from Sentinel-2 imagery; (3) Imaging spectroscopy + LiDAR-based model: PCA-reduced AVIRIS-NG imaging spectroscopy data combined with selected LiDAR-derived structural metrics (see section 2.4), to evaluate whether integrating structural information improves classification accuracy beyond imaging spectroscopy data alone; and (4) LiDAR-based model, using only airborne LiDAR-derived structural metrics.

All models were trained using the same RF configuration and validation strategy, described in section 2.5. Classification outputs were compared using standard accuracy metrics, including overall accuracy and class-level performance indicators. This comparative analysis provides insights into the relative strengths of spectral and structural data for species-level mapping in complex forest environments.

2.4. Features extraction and selection

Spectral signatures for each target species were obtained extracted from the 319 AVIRIS-NG imaging spectroscopy bands at ground reference points, resulting in 526 reflectance profiles. Approximately 30% of points were lost due to gaps between non-overlapping flightlines.

Outliers were removed using an interquartile-range (IQR) filter. For each band, the first (Q1) and third (Q3) quartiles were computed, and the IQR defined as $Q3 - Q1$. Values below $Q1 - 1.5 \times IQR$ or above $Q3 + 1.5 \times IQR$ were considered outliers and set to NA prior to analysis. The same procedure was applied to Sentinel-2 multispectral data and LiDAR-derived metrics, resulting in 709 and 747 observations, respectively.

To obtain informative metrics from LiDAR data, we used functions implemented in the ‘lidR’ package on normalized LiDAR tiles to generate 30 raster layers (2-meters resolution) characterizing elevation, intensity, number of returns and tree crown shaped for the entire study area. These metrics capture species-specific crown morphology; for example, intensity and echo width are influenced by leaf type, orientation, and foliage density (Michałowska & Rapiński, 2021; Shi et al., 2018). To reduce collinearity, metrics with a correlation coefficient greater than 0.60 were discarded.

2.5. Random Forest classification

Traditional classification algorithms (e.g. Maximum Likelihood, K-means, ISODATA) often perform poorly with imaging spectroscopy data due to its high dimensionality and limited labelled samples (Paoletti et al., 2019). Additionally, spectral similarity among species and intra-species variability further complicates accurate classification (Xie et al., 2008; Yel & Tunc Gormus, 2023; Zhong et al., 2024). Machine learning approaches (ML), including Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Random Forest (RF), and Artificial Neural Networks

(ANN), are better suited for complex, high-dimensional datasets and typically outperform traditional method in vegetation classification (Li et al., 2018; Maxwell et al., 2018; Paoletti et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2008; Zhong et al., 2024).

We employed a Random Forest (RF) algorithm, for its robustness, ease of implementation, and strong predictive performance with imaging spectroscopy data (Belgiu & Drăguț, 2016; Dalponte et al., 2013; Immitzer et al., 2012).

The RF model was implemented using the R package ‘*ranger*’ (Wright & Ziegler, 2017). Model training and parameter tuning are critical for achieving high classification accuracy. RF performance depends mainly on two parameters: the number of trees built by the model (*ntrees*) and the number of features considered at each split (*mtry*) (Belgiu & Drăguț, 2016; Breiman, 2001). The number of trees was set to 1,000, where the out-of-bag (OOB) error stabilized (Belgiu & Drăguț, 2016). The ‘*caret*’ package (Kuhn, 2008) was used to optimize hyperparameters (i.e. *mtry*, *splitrule* and *min.node.size*) via a 10-fold cross-validation. The model was trained on a random 70% subset of the input dataset.

The classification output consisted of a raster assigning each pixel to one of the five target species, accompanied by a multiband raster of class probabilities for uncertainty filtering.

Model performance was evaluated using the remaining 30% of input dataset. Global performance was assessed using area under the curve (AUC), overall accuracy (OA), weighted F1-score, and the Kappa (k) coefficient. Class-level performance was evaluated using the same metrics adjusted by class, and complemented by specificity, producer’s accuracy (PA) and user’s accuracy (UA). Predictions were also compared to species proportion reported in the 4th Swiss National Forest Inventory (NFI4; Brändli et al., 2020), as an independent reference.

2.6. Post processing

To generate a coherent tree species map, zonal statistics were applied using the ‘*terra*’ package (Hijmans, 2023). Each individual tree crown (ITC) was assigned an average prediction probability and a unique species class based on majority voting. ITC (Figure 3) were delineated from a 0.5 m resolution canopy height model (CHM) derived from airborne LiDAR point clouds. The CHM was produced using the pit-free algorithm of Khosravipour et al. (2014), implemented in the ‘*lidR*’ package with default threshold values, following normalization of LiDAR tiles and generation of a digital terrain model (DTM) using a kNN-IDW algorithm.

Crown segmentation was performed using the Dalponte and Coomes (2016) algorithm in ‘*lidR*’ package, retaining default parameters (Dalponte & Coomes, 2016) and applying concave hull method to minimize overlap between adjacent crown (Yan et al., 2019). CHM and ITC were computed for each 1 km² tile extended by a 30 m buffer to reduce edge effects.

ITC smaller than 12 m² or less than 2 m in height were filtered out to prevent the inclusion of shrubs and other non-tree objects in the analysis. To address uncertainty, pixels with the lowest 7% prediction confidence were reclassified as “Others”, consistent with species proportion reported in the NFI4 data, which reports that the five target species represent approximately 93% of trees in the park (Brändli et al., 2020).

Figure 3 – Example of individual tree crown delineation from LiDAR data. The top panel shows individual tree crown polygons (white outlines) overlaid on aerial imagery, while the bottom panel displays the corresponding Canopy Height Model (CHM) raster with crown boundaries. The CHM highlights canopy structure and tree height, supporting tree segmentation.

2.7. Gap filling with multiple point geostatistics

To address gaps in the classification map caused by incomplete imaging spectroscopy flight coverage, we applied the *chessQS* algorithm, a tile-based adaptation of the Multiple-Point Statistics (MPS) QuickSampling method (Gerber et al., 2025). Gap-filling is a common challenge in remote sensing due to data loss from clouds, sensor issues, or acquisitions inconsistencies. While various techniques exist, including spatial interpolation, geostatistical methods, and machine learning, they often struggle to maintain complex spatial structures in categorical data. MPS-based approaches overcome these limitations by reproducing higher-order spatial patterns, making them particularly effective for structurally complex environments (Gravey & Mariethoz, 2020).

The *chessQS* approach divides the image into overlapping tiles arranged in a chessboard pattern and simulates missing values using patterns extracted from a training image composed of known classifications and auxiliary covariates (e.g., elevation and RGB orthophotos). The method ensures spatial continuity across large gaps while maintaining realistic species distribution patterns. To evaluate the gap filling performance, we implemented a cross-validation strategy where synthetic gaps were introduced into 14 reference tiles and filled using 10 stochastic realizations of *chessQS*. The spatial structure of the species was assessed by computing the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between normalized indicator variograms of reference and simulated data for all tree species class within the cross-validation tiles. This approach evaluates whether the simulations reproduce the spatial continuity of species patterns by comparing semi-variance at multiple lags, where lower or higher values than the reference indicate smoother or more heterogeneous simulated structures, respectively. To test individual-tree agreement, we computed the Overall, User's, and Producer's Accuracies. A detailed description of the algorithm, the cross-validation framework, the implementation, and the resulting analyses of the performance of the gap-filling are presented in Gerber et al. (2025).

3. Results

3.1. Features extraction and selection

Spectral signatures of the five target species were extracted from imaging spectroscopy data at ground reference points (Figure 4). These profiles reveal clear differences between deciduous species (*Acer pseudoplatanus*, Ap; *Fraxinus excelsior*, Fe; *Fagus sylvatica*, Fs) and conifer species (*Abies alba*, Aa; *Picea abies*, Pa), particularly at wavelengths below 1,304 nm. Spectral signatures from the multispectral imagery are provided in Appendix 1.

Following dimensionality reduction via PCA, the first 13 principal components were retained for modeling, explaining 99.92% of the variance (Appendix 2).

Figure 4 – Tree species’ spectral signatures from imaging spectroscopy data. Average reflectance profiles for five dominant species across wavelengths 412-1,304 nm, 1,464-1,774 nm and 2,030-2,411 nm, illustrating distinct spectral patterns useful for classification.

Of the 30 LiDAR-derived metrics computed (Appendix 3), 9 were selected after correlation analysis (Appendix 4), representing height (3), intensity (4) and crown shape (2) characteristics (Table 1).

Table 1 – Selected LiDAR-derived metrics used for tree species classification. Nine structural features were retained after correlation analysis, grouped into elevation, intensity, and crown shape categories. These metrics capture species-specific canopy characteristics and support model differentiation.

Metric category	Description	Covariate name
Elevation	Maximum height	zmax
	Kurtosis of height distribution	zkurt
	5 th quantile of height distribution	zq5
Intensity	Sum of intensities for each return	itot
	Standard deviation of intensity	isd
	Kurtosis of intensity distribution	ikurt
	Percentage of intensity returned below the 10th percentile of height	ipcumzq10
Shape	Intermediate eigenvalue indicating secondary direction of point cloud variation	eigen_medium
	Local surface irregularity of bending	curvature

3.2. Tree species map

The tree species classification map generated from imaging spectroscopy data illustrates the spatial distribution of the five dominant species across the study area (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Tree species classification map. This map shows the spatial distribution of the five main tree species in the study area, obtained by classifying imaging spectroscopy data using a Random Forest model. Each color represents a species class, with “Others” indicating low-confidence predictions reclassified as non-target species. Insets show zoomed-in examples of local forest composition, illustrating the model’s ability to capture fine-scale species patterns. The map highlights dominant broadleaves species (*Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Fagus sylvatica*) in valleys areas, and coniferous species (*Abies alba*, *Picea abies*) at higher elevations, consistent with ecological expectations (Lauber et al., 2018).

Deciduous species are concentrated in valley regions, while conifers dominate higher elevations. Species proportions are summarized in Table 2: Pa is most prevalent, accounting for 52% of the classified trees, followed by Fs (27%), Aa (7%), Fe (5%) and Ap (3%). The “Others” represents for 7% of the predicted trees.

Table 2 – Predicted and expected tree species proportions. Comparison of species prevalence from classification model with reference data from the 4th Swiss National Forest Inventory (Brändli et al., 2020). The proportions remain broadly like those expected in the reference dataset, with *Picea abies* being the most common species and *Fagus sylvatica* coming in second place in each case. The other 3 species are much less prevalent, with a clear underrepresentation of *Abies alba*.

	Predicted proportion	Expected proportion
	Classified imaging spectroscopy data	4 th National Forest Inventory
<i>Abies alba</i>	0.07	0.15
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	0.03	0.08
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	0.05	0.03
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	0.27	0.12
<i>Picea abies</i>	0.52	0.55

<i>Others</i>	0.07	0.07
---------------	------	------

Overall, the model achieved satisfactory performance (Table 3, Figures 6-7) with an overall accuracy of 74%. However, classification accuracy varies among species, particularly Aa and Pa, which were frequently misclassified, as it is illustrated in confusion matrix (Figure 7), while Fs or Fe were predicted with greater confidence.

Table 3 – Classification performance metrics by species and overall, obtained against validation data. Summary of per-class sensitivity, specificity, and balanced accuracy for the imaging spectroscopy based model, along with global metrics (overall accuracy, weighted F1-score, Kappa coefficient and Area Under the Curve).

	Abies alba	Acer pseudoplatanus	Fraxinus excelsior	Fagus sylvatica	Picea abies	Std. deviation
Sensitivity	0.38	0.48	0.85	0.93	0.91	0.26
Specificity	0.99	0.97	0.92	0.95	0.84	0.06
Balanced accuracy	0.68	0.73	0.89	0.94	0.88	0.11
Global						
Overall accuracy	0.74					
Weighted F1-score	0.73					
Kappa	0.67					
AUC	0.75					

3.3. Comparative analysis of multispectral, imaging spectroscopy and LiDAR-based models

The four RF models produced distinct classification outcomes. The imaging spectroscopy-LiDAR fusion model achieved the highest overall performance, with a weighted F1-score of 0.75, a Kappa coefficient of 0.70 and an AUC of 0.76, slightly outperforming the imaging spectroscopy only model (weighted F1-score: 0.73; Kappa: 0.67; AUC: 0.75). In contrast, the multispectral model delivered substantially lower accuracy (weighted F1-score: 0.41; Kappa: 0.28; AUC: 0.64), while the LiDAR-based model performed poorest (weighted F1-score: 0.36; Kappa: 0.20; AUC: 0.63) (Figure 6; Appendices 5-6-7).

Figure 6 - Classification performance metrics across different data sources, including both overall and class-level values. The data sources include imaging spectroscopy data combined with LiDAR, imaging spectroscopy alone, multispectral imagery, and LiDAR alone. “Accuracy” refers to overall accuracy for the overall values and to user’s accuracy (sensitivity) for class-level values. Metrics shown include F1-score, Kappa, and AUC (area under the curve).

The imaging spectroscopy-LiDAR fusion model delivered consistently high performance across most species (Figure 6). Fe and Fs achieved the highest F1-scores (0.82 and 0.81), while Aa and Ap had the lowest (0.60 and 0.68), indicating lower classification performance. Notably, Aa reached perfect user’s accuracy (1.00), meaning all predicted Aa samples were correct (Figure 7); however, its producer’s accuracy remained low (0.43), reflecting frequent misclassification of true Aa individuals, often as Pa. Compared to the imaging spectroscopy only model, adding LiDAR data improved Aa classification, increasing user’s accuracy from 0.80 to 1.00 and producer’s accuracy from 0.38 to 0.43. Overall, LiDAR integration improved F1-scores across all classes (Figure 6). Although overall performance was lower, the multispectral model achieved the highest producer’s accuracy for Aa (0.77), and its highest F1-score (0.64) (Figure 7).

Figure 7 – Confusion matrices for tree species classification models. Comparison of prediction accuracy across the four Random Forest models using different remote sensing inputs. Imaging spectroscopy data, imaging spectroscopy data + LiDAR, multispectral imagery, and LiDAR only. Each matrix shows the distribution of predicted vs reference species, with user and producer’s accuracies (UA, PA), overall accuracies (OA) and Kappa (k) coefficients indicating model performance. The relative frequency is represented in shades of blue; the higher the frequency, the better the class is discriminated by the model. The number of samples for each method differs due to: (1) the outlier removal step, applied across each dataset, and (2) gaps in imaging spectroscopy flightlines vs. full coverage for multispectral and LiDAR data (see section 2.4).

3.4. Post processing and gap filling with multiple point geostatistics

The gap-filled tree species map showed seamless transitions between original and simulated regions, visually preserving species variability (Figure 8). Spatial analysis confirmed this coherence with variograms for reference and simulated data indicating strong agreement in spatial structure, with low error values across species categories (mean RMSE, Table 4).

Table 4 – Evaluation of gap-filling performance. Metrics summarize the ability of the chessQS algorithm to reconstruct missing areas while preserving the spatial structure and the classification accuracy. The mean Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between the normalized indicator variograms of the reference and simulated gaps quantify differences in spatial patterns. Lower RMSE indicates better structural consistency. Classification accuracy is evaluated using user’s accuracy (UA) and producer’s accuracy (PA). Values have been computed for all classes (Aa = *Abies alba*; Ap = *Acer pseudoplatanus*; Fe = *Fraxinus excelsior*; Fs = *Fagus sylvatica*; Pa = *Picea abies*) with 10 chessQS realizations for each of the 14 cross-validation tiles. Adapted from Gerber et al. (2025).

	Aa	Ap	Fe	Fs	Pa	Others
Mean RMSE	0.061	0.117	0.183	0.063	0.068	0.091
UA	0.159	0.052	0.091	0.290	0.313	0.097
PA	0.212	0.026	0.038	0.185	0.395	0.071

Local classification accuracy remained limited across the cross-validation tiles (Overall Accuracy = 0.279; User and producer’s accuracy, Table 4).

Figure 8 – Tree species classification map before and after gap filling. Panel A shows the initial classification map derived from imaging spectroscopy-LiDAR fusion model, with visible gaps between flightlines (outlined in cyan). Panel B presents the final map after applying the chessQS gap-filling method (Gerber et al., 2025), resulting in a spatially continuous and coherent species distribution. This step ensures full coverage of the study area while preserving realistic spatial patterns.

4. Discussion

4.1. Contribution of imaging spectroscopy data for vegetation mapping

The spatial distribution of the five target species across the study area aligns with ecological expectations (Lauber et al., 2018): conifers (*Abies alba*, Aa; *Picea abies*, Pa) dominate higher elevations, while deciduous species (*Acer pseudoplatanus*, Ap; *Fraxinus excelsior*, Fe; *Fagus sylvatica*, Fs) are concentrated in valleys (Lauber et al., 2018). Predicted proportions generally match those expected based on the 4th National Forest Inventory, although Fs is overrepresented (27% vs. 12%) and *Abies alba* is underrepresented (7% vs. 15%) (Table 2).

The imaging spectroscopy based model achieved strong performance, with an accuracy of 74% (Table 3), comparable to results reported by Behera et al. (2021) and Dalponte et al. (2012), and higher than those of Badola et al. (2021). The AUC (0.75) indicates substantial agreement (Hosmer & Lemeshow, 2000). Class-level metrics highlight significant variability in the model's ability to distinguish between species (Table 3). Fe and Fs were classified with high sensitivity and specificity (Fe: 0.85/0.92; Fs: 0.93/0.95), whereas Aa showed the lowest sensitivity (0.38) despite high specificity (0.99), reflecting frequent misclassification as Pa. Ap also exhibited low sensitivity (0.48), often confused with other broadleaves (mainly Fe). These errors likely stem from spectral overlap and the underrepresentation of Aa in sampled trees ($n = 110$, i.e., 15% of ground reference points) and by extension in the training dataset ($n = 46$,

i.e., 12%), suggesting that more balanced sampling could improve performance (Fassnacht et al., 2016).

Although the multispectral-based model performed worse overall (accuracy: 42% vs. 74%; Figures 6, 7), its performance is notable given the much coarser spatial resolution (20 m) and limited spectral information compared to AVIRIS-NG. Despite using more training points (502 vs. 371), the multispectral model could not match the imaging spectroscopy model's ability to discriminate species, particularly between conifers and broadleaves. Interestingly, Aa achieved relatively strong results in the multispectral model, likely due to distinctive reflectance patterns in Sentinel-2 bands (Appendix 1).

These findings highlight the superior discriminative power of imaging spectroscopy data for species-level mapping. However, they also raise an important consideration: given the universal availability and low cost of Sentinel-2 imagery, its relatively good performance, even under these constraints, suggests that multispectral approaches may offer a practical alternative for large-scale applications where imaging spectroscopy data acquisition is cost-prohibitive.

Beyond methodological advances, producing a continuous, high-resolution tree species map has significant implications for forest management and conservation. Such maps enable park managers to identify ecological hotspots, monitor biodiversity dynamics, detect invasive species, and plan targeted conservation actions (Choe et al., 2025; Reddy, 2021). Forest services can leverage species distribution data to optimize silvicultural practices, assess timber resources, and anticipate climate-driven shift in forest composition (Weinstein et al., 2024). They also support risk management by identifying species vulnerable to pests, diseases, or drought, enabling proactive interventions (Choe et al., 2025). In ecological modeling, species-level maps improve estimates of biomass, carbon storage and other nature's contributions to people by incorporating species-specific traits (Wickham & Riitters, 2019), while facilitating long-term monitoring and evaluation of forest efforts. In the GPH park, this map represents a valuable decision-support tool for current and future management planning. Remote sensing approaches, particularly in mountainous areas with limited field accessibility, offer a scalable and cost-effective alternative to traditional surveys, ensuring broad coverage and high precision. Such map would directly contribute to strategic objectives related to biodiversity conservation, sustainable forestry, and ecological infrastructure development (Pays-d'Enhaut, 2021).

4.2. Added value of LiDAR-derived features

LiDAR data are widely recognized for their ability to capture detailed forest structure (Balestra et al., 2024). In this study, integrating LiDAR-derived metrics with imaging spectroscopy data resulted in only modest improvements in classification accuracy (Figure 6), overall accuracy increased from 74% to 76% and yielded marginal gains for class-specific metrics, notably Aa (sensitivity went up from 0.38 to 0.43, and specificity from 0.99 to 1.00) and Pa (sensitivity increased from 0.91 to 0.94, specificity from 0.84 to 0.87) (Table 3; Appendix 6).

These results suggest that spectral information remains the primary driver of species discrimination: in our model, spectral variables consistently rank higher in importance than structural metrics (Appendix 8), suggesting that species-level differences are more effectively captured through reflectance than crown architecture. Although LiDAR integration increases

processing complexity and computational demands, its use may be justified in applications where structural traits are critical.

These findings align with recent literature: Balestra et al. (2024) in their review highlight that while imaging spectroscopy-LiDAR fusion often yields modest, context-dependent gains. In our case, imaging spectroscopy data alone provided strong classification performance, and LiDAR's contribution was secondary. Future work could explore more advanced fusion techniques, such as deep learning models that jointly learn from spectral and structural data, or the use of full-waveform LiDAR, which may capture more nuanced structural traits (Liao et al., 2018; Wang & Jiang, 2024).

4.3. Multiple point geostatistics for gap filling

The *chessQS* algorithm proved effective for gap-filling in the tree species classification map, preserving spatial structure across large, heterogeneous areas. The method produced visually coherent results with no abrupt transitions between simulated and reference regions and maintained species distribution patterns (Gerber et al., 2025). However, pixel-level accuracy remained low, likely due to weak correlations between covariates and species presence. This suggests that while *chessQS* effectively reproduces broader spatial patterns, it cannot ensure pixel-level accuracy in large gaps when covariates are not sufficiently informative. The *chessQS* algorithm prioritizes reproducing realistic spatial patterns over local accuracy, ensuring coherent and plausible results even with weak or missing covariates. These findings support the use of *chessQS* in situations where covariates are unavailable or have low predictive power, yet realistic spatial patterns are still required. In such cases, *chessQS* reliably reconstructs coherent spatial structure even when meaningful predictors are lacking.

4.4. Limitations

Random Forest is highly dependent on the quality of training data (Belgiu & Drăguț, 2016). Consequently, field data should meet key criteria (Belgiu & Drăguț, 2016; Fassnacht et al., 2016): (1) accurate species identification to minimize errors; (2) balanced representation of all classes; and (3) sufficient sample size relative to data dimensionality, particularly for imaging spectroscopy data. Although our sampling plan followed the aforementioned criteria, two challenges emerged: the complex topography of the study area limited uniform coverage, and incomplete imaging spectroscopy data coverage resulted in the loss of approximately 30% of ground reference points. This study spans a large area and involves extensive datasets, requiring substantial resources for data collection, processing and analysis, which constrained some methodological choices. Despite these limitations, classification results remained robust, highlighting the strong potential of imaging spectroscopy data for species-level mapping.

4.5. Perspectives

High-resolution species maps open new opportunities for forest ecology, management and conservation. Future research should focus on expanding species coverage, integrating temporal monitoring to capture phenological dynamics (Dronova & Taddeo, 2022), and improving classification robustness through advanced data fusion techniques, such as deep learning models that jointly exploit spectral, structural and temporal information (Matyukira & Mhangara, 2024).

Emerging technologies, including full-waveform LiDAR and next-generation imaging spectroscopy sensors, offer opportunities to refine structural and biochemical trait detection,

enabling more accurate species discrimination and ecosystem modeling (Fassnacht et al., 2023; Oberoi, 2025). Coupling these datasets with climate projections could enhance predictive models of forest composition under global change, supporting adaptive management strategies (Cavender-Bares et al., 2022).

Democratizing access to high-resolution remote sensing data remains a critical challenge. While imaging spectroscopy data delivers superior accuracy, its high cost and limited availability raise questions about scalability (Dritsas & Trigka, 2025). Future efforts should explore hybrid approaches that leverage freely available multispectral data (e.g., Sentinel-2) alongside targeted imaging spectroscopy data acquisitions to balance precision and affordability (Glowienka & Zembol, 2022; Kluczek et al., 2023).

Ultimately, advancing these methods will strengthen our ability to monitor biodiversity, quantify nature's contributions to people, and inform policy decisions for sustainable forest management (Wickham & Riitters, 2019). This research underscores the need for collaborative frameworks that integrate remote sensing, field ecology, and computational modeling to address the complex challenges posed by climate change and land-use pressures (Cavender-Bares et al., 2022).

5. Conclusion

This study presents the first use of AVIRIS-NG imaging spectroscopy data for tree species classification in the Swiss Pre-Alps, demonstrating the feasibility and strong potential of imaging spectroscopy for detailed forest monitoring in complex mountainous area. By leveraging imaging spectroscopy data with LiDAR-derived structural metrics, we achieved robust species-level classification of individual tree crowns for five dominant species.

Among the tested approaches, imaging spectroscopy and LiDAR data fusion yielded the best classification performance. Although the addition of LiDAR-derived structural features led to a modest improvement in overall accuracy (from 74% to 76%), suggesting that spectral information remains the primary driver of model performance, LiDAR may still offer complementary value in distinguishing species with similar spectral signatures, such as *Abies alba* and *Picea abies*.

The integration of a novel gap-filling method (*chessQS*) enabled the production of a continuous species map, preserving realistic spatial patterns despite incomplete flight coverage. Although pixel-level accuracy in gap-filled areas remains limited, this method offers a practical solution for large-scale mapping in heterogeneous landscapes. This approach is likely to enhance the utility of the final product for forest monitoring, biodiversity conservation, and adaptive management in the context of climate change.

Future work should explore more advanced fusion techniques to enhance classification robustness and potentially increase the number of species classified. Efforts to facilitate access and use high-resolution remote sensing data, through hybrid approaches combining freely available multispectral imagery with targeted imaging spectroscopy data acquisitions, will be critical for scaling these methods. Ultimately, this research delivers tools that can support sustainable forest management, biodiversity conservation, and informed decision-making under global change.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The Authors report no potential conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

We gratefully acknowledge the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) and especially the AVIRIS-NG team for acquiring, processing, and providing access to the AVIRIS-NG data used in this study, as well as Dr. Andreas Hüni for his role of principal investigator in this data campaign.

The authors would like to thank the Ecospat group (A. Guisan, university of Lausanne) and particularly Dr. Olivier Broennimann for lending GPS equipment.

Data Availability Statement

Source data can be accessed through <https://avirisng.jpl.nasa.gov/dataportal/>. Reprojected and geometrically corrected flightlines are available on request.

Scripts are available on GitHub repository: https://github.com/ALambiel/GPH_treemap

Tree classification map is available on online repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17805682>.

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International data waiver.

Funding

This work was supported by the Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) through the ValPar.CH project (<https://valpar.ch/>); the Institute for Environmental Sciences of University of Geneva; and the Digital Science Centre for the Environment and Health SDES.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used the DeepL language model to support English writing, and to a limited extent, ChatGPT to assist with proofreading. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the article.

Author Contributions

Audrey Lambiel: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Funding acquisition, **Loïc Gerber:** Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, **Anna Schweiger:** Resources, Writing – review & editing, **Mathias Kneubühler:** Resources, Writing – review & editing, **Grégoire Mariéthoz:** Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, **Anthony Lehmann:** Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, **Nathan Külling:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision

6. References

Ahmad, S., et al. (2021). Potential of hyperspectral AVIRIS-NG data for vegetation characterization, species spectral separability, and mapping. *Appl. Geomat.*, 13(3), 361-372. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12518-021-00355-6>

- Badola, A., et al. (2021). Tree species mapping in tropical forests using hyperspectral remote sensing and machine learning [Conference proceedings]. 2021 IEEE IGARSS, Brussels, Belgium. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS47720.2021.9553549>
- Balestra, M., et al. (2024). LiDAR data fusion to improve forest attribute estimates: A review. *Curr. For. Rep.*, 10(4), 281-297. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40725-024-00223-7>
- Behera, M. D., et al. (2021). Species-level classification and mapping of a mangrove forest using random forest—utilisation of AVIRIS-NG and Sentinel data. *Remote Sens.*, 13(11), 2027. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13112027>
- Belgiu, M., & Drăguț, L. (2016). Random forest in remote sensing: A review of applications and future directions. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, 114, 24-31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2016.01.011>
- Brändli, U.-B., et al. (2020). *Inventaire forestier national suisse. Résultats du quatrième inventaire 2009-2017* (Birmensdorf, Institut fédéral de recherches sur la forêt, la neige et le paysage WSL ; Berne, Office fédéral de l'environnement. <https://doi.org/10.16904/ENVIDAT.147>
- Breiman, L. (2001). Random Forests. *Mach. Learn.*, 45(1), 5-32. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324>
- Cavender-Bares, J., et al. (2022). Integrating remote sensing with ecology and evolution to advance biodiversity conservation. *Nat. Ecol. Evo.*, 6(5), 506-519. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-022-01702-5>
- CH2018. (2018). *CH2018 – Climate scenarios for Switzerland, technical report*. NCCS. https://scnat.ch/en/uuid/i/c90bffe5-11c6-5501-829f-3d25e5fea29a-CH2018_%E2%80%93_Climate_Scenarios_for_Switzerland_Technical_Report
- Choe, T., et al. (2025). From coarse to crisp: Enhancing tree species maps with deep learning and satellite imagery. *Remote Sens.*, 17(13), 2222. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs17132222>
- Dalponte, M., et al. (2012). Tree species classification in the Southern Alps based on the fusion of very high geometrical resolution multispectral/hyperspectral images and LiDAR data. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 123, 258-270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.03.013>
- Dalponte, M., & Coomes, D. A. (2016). Tree-centric mapping of forest carbon density from airborne laser scanning and hyperspectral data. *Methods Ecol. Evol.*, 7(10), 1236-1245. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12575>
- Dalponte, M., et al. (2014). Tree crown delineation and tree species classification in boreal forests using hyperspectral and ALS data. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 140, 306-317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2013.09.006>
- Dalponte, M., et al. (2013). Tree species classification in boreal forests with hyperspectral data. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, 51(5), 2632-2645. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2012.2216272>
- Díaz, S., et al. (2018). Assessing nature's contributions to people. *Sci.*, 359(6373), 270-272. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap8826>
- Dritsas, E., & Trigka, M. (2025). Remote sensing and geospatial analysis in the Big Data era: A Survey. *Remote Sens.*, 17(3), 550. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs17030550>
- Dronova, I., & Taddeo, S. (2022). Remote sensing of phenology: Towards the comprehensive indicators of plant community dynamics from species to regional scales. *J. Ecol.*, 110(7), 1460-1484. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.13897>
- Exelis Visual Information, S. (2023). *ENVI*. In https://www.l3harrisgeospatial.com/Portals/0/pdfs/NV5_ENVI_WEB.pdf
- Fassnacht, F. E., et al. (2016). Review of studies on tree species classification from remotely sensed data. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 186, 64-87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2016.08.013>

- Fassnacht, F. E., et al. (2023). Remote sensing in forestry: current challenges, considerations and directions. *Int. J. For. Res.*, 97(1), 11-37. <https://doi.org/10.1093/forestry/cpad024>
- Gerber, L., et al. (2025). chessQS: an efficient tile-based gap-filling method for large and complex remote sensing images (preprint). *SSRN*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5419005>
- Ghiyammat, A., & Shafri, H. Z. M. (2010). A review on hyperspectral remote sensing for homogeneous and heterogeneous forest biodiversity assessment. *Int. J. Remote Sens.*, 31(7), 1837-1856. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160902926681>
- Gholizadeh, H., et al. (2019). Detecting prairie biodiversity with airborne remote sensing. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 221, 38-49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.10.037>
- Glowienka, E., & Zembol, N. (2022). Forest community mapping using hyperspectral (CHRIS/PROBA) and Sentinel-2 multispectral images. *Geomat. Environ. Eng.*, 16(4), 103-117. <https://doi.org/10.7494/geom.2022.16.4.103>
- Gravey, M., & Mariethoz, G. (2020). QuickSampling v1.0: a robust and simplified pixel-based multiple-point simulation approach. *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 13(6), 2611-2630. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-2611-2020>
- Guisan, A., et al. (2013). Predicting species distributions for conservation decisions. *Ecol. Lett.*, 16(12), 1424-1435. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12189>
- Hijmans, R. (2023). terra : Spatial Data Analysis. R package version 1.6-17. In.
- Hosmer, D. W., & Lemeshow, S. (2000). Area under the ROC curve. In *Applied Logistic Regression* (2nd ed., pp. 160-164). John Wiley and Sons.
- Immitzer, M., et al. (2012). Tree species classification with Random Forest using very high spatial resolution 8-band WorldView-2 satellite data. *Remote Sens.*, 4(9), 2661-2693. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs4092661>
- Jha, C. S., et al. (2019). Characterization of species diversity and forest health using AVIRIS-NG hyperspectral remote sensing data. *Curr. Sci.*, 116(7), 1124-1135. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27138004>
- Jiang, Y., et al. (2025). Assessing the potential of multi-seasonal Sentinel-2 satellite imagery combined with airborne LiDAR for urban tree species identification. *Sci. Rep.*, 15(1), 25107. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-10971-6>
- Jin, X. (2018). ENVI automated image registration solutions. In: Harris Corporation.
- Khosravipour, A., et al. (2014). Generating pit-free canopy height models from airborne lidar. *Photogramm. Eng. Remote Sens.*, 80(9), 863-872. <https://doi.org/10.14358/PERS.80.9.863>
- Kluczek, M., et al. (2023). Mountain tree species mapping using Sentinel-2, PlanetScope, and airborne HySpex hyperspectral imagery. *Remote Sens.*, 15(3), 844. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15030844>
- Kothari, S., & Schweiger, A. K. (2022). Plant spectra as integrative measures of plant phenotypes. *J. Ecol.*, 110(11), 2536-2554. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2745.13972>
- Kuhn, M. (2008). Building predictive models in R using the caret package. *J. Stat. Soft.*, 28(5). <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v028.i05>
- Lahoz-Monfort, J. J., & Magrath, M. J. L. (2021). A comprehensive overview of technologies for species and habitat monitoring and conservation. *Biosci.*, 71(10), 1038-1062. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biab073>
- Lauber, K., et al. (2018). *Flora Helvetica: flore illustrée de Suisse* (5 ed.). Haupt.
- Li, Y., et al. (2018). Deep learning for remote sensing image classification: A survey. *WIREs Data Min. Knowl.*, 8(6), e1264. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1264>
- Liao, W., et al. (2018). Deep learning for fusion of APEX hyperspectral and full-waveform LiDAR remote sensing data for tree species mapping. *IEEE Access*, 6, 68716-68729. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2880083>

- Matyukira, C., & Mhangara, P. (2024). Advances in vegetation mapping through remote sensing and machine learning techniques: A scientometric review. *Eur. J. Remote Sens.*, 57(1), 2422330. <https://doi.org/10.1080/22797254.2024.2422330>
- Maxwell, A. E., et al. (2018). Implementation of machine-learning classification in remote sensing: An applied review. *Int. J. Remote Sens.*, 39(9), 2784-2817. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2018.1433343>
- Michałowska, M., & Rapiński, J. (2021). A review of tree species classification based on airborne LiDAR data and applied classifiers. *Remote Sens.*, 13(3), 353. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13030353>
- Mori, A. S., et al. (2017). Biodiversity and ecosystem services in forest ecosystems: a research agenda for applied forest ecology. *J. Appl. Ecol.*, 54(1), 12-27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12669>
- Oberoi, I. (2025). Advancements in multi-spectral and hyperspectral remote sensing: techniques, applications, and future directions. *J. Adv. Res. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, 12(1&2), 6-11. <https://thejournalshouse.com/index.php/geoscience-remotesensing-earth/article/view/1451>
- OFEV. (2021). *Forest Policy: objectives and measures 2021-2024. For the sustainable management of forests in Switzerland. First revised edition 2021.* (Environmental Info, Issue. <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/dam/bafu/en/dokumente/wald-holz/ud-umwelt-diverses/waldpolitik-zieleundmassnahmen2024.pdf.download.pdf/forest-policy-objectivesandmeasures2024.pdf>
- OFEV. (2022). *Annuaire La forêt et le bois 2022* (Etat de l'environnement, Issue. https://www.bafu.admin.ch/dam/bafu/fr/dokumente/wald-holz/uz-umwelt-zustand/jahrbuch-wald-und-holz-2022.pdf.download.pdf/UZ-2225-F_JB-WaldHolz%202022.pdf
- OFEV/WSL. (2025). *Forest Report 2025. Development, condition and use of Swiss forests.* <https://www.dora.lib4ri.ch/wsl/islandora/object/ws:37786>
- Olschewski, R., et al. (2018). Policy Forum: Challenges and opportunities in developing new forest governance systems: Insights from the IPBES assessment for Europe and Central Asia. *For. Policy Econ.*, 97, 175-179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.10.007>
- Paoletti, M. E., et al. (2019). Deep learning classifiers for hyperspectral imaging: A review. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, 158, 279-317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2019.09.006>
- Pays-d'Enhaut, P. G. (2021). *Charte du Parc naturel régional Gruyère Pays-d'Enhaut (2022 - 2031)*. P. G. Pays-d'Enhaut. <https://www.gruyerepaysdenhaut.ch/fr/documentation>
- Pays-d'Enhaut, P. G. (2025, 2025-08-20). *Présentation du parc.* <https://www.gruyerepaysdenhaut.ch>
- Plakman, V., et al. (2020). Mapping species at an individual-tree scale in a temperate forest, using Sentinel-2 images, airborne laser scanning data, and Random Forest classification. *Remote Sens.*, 12(22), 3710. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12223710>
- Quan, Y., et al. (2023). Tree species classification in a typical natural secondary forest using UAV-borne LiDAR and hyperspectral data. *GISci. Remote Sens.*, 60(1), 2171706. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15481603.2023.2171706>
- R Core Team. (2022). *R: A language and environment for statistical computing.* In R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Reddy, C. S. (2021). Remote sensing of biodiversity: what to measure and monitor from space to species? *Biodivers. Conserv.*, 30(10), 2617-2631. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-021-02216-5>

- Roussel, J.-R., et al. (2020). lidR: An R package for analysis of Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) data. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 251, 112061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.112061>
- Schweiger, A. K. (2021). L'écologie rencontre la télédétection - Imagerie hyperspectrale dans le Parc naturel régional Gruyère Pays-d'Enhaut. In.
- Shi, Y., et al. (2018). Tree species classification using plant functional traits from LiDAR and hyperspectral data. *Int. J. Appl. Earth Obs. Geoinf.*, 73, 207-219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2018.06.018>
- Strassburg, B. B. N., et al. (2020). Global priority areas for ecosystem restoration. *Nat.*, 586(7831), 724-729. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2784-9>
- Swisstopo. (2021). *swissSURFACE3D*. <https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/fr/geodata/height/surface3d.html>
- Swisstopo. (2022a). *swissALTI3D*. <https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/fr/geodata/height/alti3d.html>
- Swisstopo. (2022b). *SWISSIMAGE 10 cm*. <https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/fr/geodata/images/ortho/swissimage10.html>
- Trimble, I. (2015). In. Westminster, USA.
- UN. (2017). *United Nations strategic plan for forests 2017-2030*. <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/n17/115/46/pdf/n1711546.pdf>
- Walpole, M., et al. (2017). Using data for decision-making: From observations to indicators and other policy tools. In M. Walters & R. J. Scholes (Eds.), *The GEO Handbook on Biodiversity Observation Networks* (pp. 293-308). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-27288-7_12
- Wang, B., et al. (2023). UAV LiDAR and hyperspectral data synergy for tree species classification in the maershan forest farm region. *Remote Sens.*, 15(4), 1000. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15041000>
- Wang, J., & Jiang, Y. (2024). A Hybrid convolution neural network for the classification of tree species using hyperspectral imagery. *PLOS One*, 19(5), e0304469. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0304469>
- Wang, Q., et al. (2023). A comprehensive review of spatial-temporal-spectral information reconstruction techniques. *Sci. Remote Sens.*, 8, 100102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.srs.2023.100102>
- Wang, Z., et al. (2019). Mapping foliar functional traits and their uncertainties across three years in a grassland experiment. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, 221, 405-416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2018.11.016>
- Weinstein, B. G., et al. (2024). Individual canopy tree species maps for the National Ecological Observatory Network. *PLOS Biol.*, 22(7), e3002700. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3002700>
- Wickham, J., & Riitters, K. H. (2019). Influence of high-resolution data on the assessment of forest fragmentation. *Landsc. Ecol.*, 34(9), 2169-2182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-019-00820-z>
- Wright, M. N., & Ziegler, A. (2017). Ranger : a fast implementation of Random Forests for high dimensional data in C++ and R. *J. Stat. Soft.*, 77(1). <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v077.i01>
- Xie, Y., et al. (2008). Remote sensing imagery in vegetation mapping: a review. *J. Plant Ecol.*, 1(1), 9-23. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpe/rtm005>
- Yan, Z., et al. (2019). A concave hull methodology for calculating the crown volume of individual trees based on vehicle-borne LiDAR data. *Remote Sens.*, 11(6), 623. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11060623>

- Yel, S. G., & Tunc Gormus, E. (2023). Exploiting hyperspectral and multispectral images in the detection of tree species: A review [Review]. *Front. Remote Sens.*, *Volume 4 - 2023*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsen.2023.1136289>
- Zhong, L., et al. (2024). A review: Tree species classification based on remote sensing data and classic deep learning-based methods. *For.*, *15(5)*, 852. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f15050852>